

ETHICAL LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS OF LUGUS DISTRICT, MINISTRY OF BASIC, HIGHER AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION – SULU: TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES

Peñon M. Halilulla

Guimba Pait Primary School, Pait, Lugus Sulu

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ABSTRACT

The study is a descriptive research which deals with the extent of leadership skills of elementary school administrators of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu. Along with discussing the demographic profiles of the teacher respondents in terms of gender, educational attainment, marital status, and length of service, it also discusses the level of leadership that the elementary school administrators of MBHTE – Sulu, Lugus District, possess in terms of dependability, decisiveness, integrity, and problem solving. It also deals with the significant difference in the extent of leadership skills of elementary school administrators of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to demographic profile in terms of gender, educational attainment, civil status, and length of service, and the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by teachers at Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu. The study was conducted at Lugus District. The respondents of the study are the elementary school teachers of Lugus District. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents of the study. The research instrument is composed of two parts. Part I is about the demographic profile of the respondents which includes their gender, educational attainment, civil status, and length of service. Part II is composed of 10 statements each on decisiveness, integrity, problem solving, and dependability. There are 5 levels to choose from which ranges from “always” to “never”. It was found that female respondents comprise the majority, finished baccalaureate degree only, mostly married, and quite old in the service. The respondents indicated **often** to decisiveness, integrity, and dependability. However, they indicated **sometimes** to problem solving. There is no significant difference in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary

school administrators as perceived by teachers of Lugus District in terms of demographic profile. There is a very high to high correlation among the four factors.

Keywords: *Ethical Leadership Skills, MBHTE-SULU, Teacher's Perspective, Elementary School Administrator, Descriptive Research*

INTRODUCTION

Leaders that are ethical honors everyone, from their superiors to their employees, equally. Ethical leadership skills of school administrator are one of the crucial factors that can affect teaching and learning practices in formal education. The school administrator faces many components of the educational problem that requires specific ethical leadership skills to address these components. Decisions making is one from the skills sufficient to develop solutions of the problems met. The school administrator equipped with decision making techniques would be easily developed solutions to the school problem. Another special skills of an ethical leader should possess is integrity, moral principles or professional standards. Since, the educational school systems are composed of mainly the students, teachers and the school administrator. The school administrator does not only focus his attention in the consequences of academic importance, but also consider the relationship among the teachers and students as well. Hence the ethical leadership skills of school administrator should develop team building strategies, which eventually contribute to the improvement of academic excellence. Collaborative efforts of the teachers and school administrator to address common problems in academic performance easily overcome the consequences of poor teaching and learning performance. The improvement of academic performance in the formal school system cannot be accomplished with the sole movement of the school administrator alone. As much as possible the whole school classroom teachers, and stakeholders must consider the problem of poor academic performance, thus the school administrator must possess with ethical leadership skills of dependability. The stakeholders support the school administrator when the school administrator can be trust. The support of the teachers, parents and stakeholders, of course, identify according to the task they can be utilized for solving the specific problem. But, appropriately, the school administrator can take the responsibility of distributing the task to be accomplished by individuals or group for purposes of improving academic performance and school development as a whole.

Poor ethical behavior and a lack of ethical leadership abilities are two of the biggest issues facing businesses today, according to a thorough qualitative study by Plinio, Young, and Lavery (2010). As such, the authors observe that a sluggish economy is making matters worse and that public confidence in leadership is declining. The authors also saw a concerning rise in employee malfeasance across the board. According to

Darcy (2010), there is currently skepticism about ethics in organizations. According to the results of a qualitative study the author conducted, 66% of respondents doubt the existence of ethics in leadership. The author describes this as "a crisis of trust."

The study's result indicated that a lack of trust is currently the largest issue facing both individuals and businesses. The "shadow side" of leadership, as defined by Frank (2002), is the cause of this lack of trust. The negative effects of "power, privilege, deception, inconsistency, irresponsibility, and misplaced loyalties" are among these shadows. Unfortunately, followers eventually learn about the negative effects of these covert actions and come to doubt the honesty of their leader. This has sparked a wave of studies and publications on the subject of moral leadership abilities. According to Yukl (2006), an ethical leader is one who upholds integrity and aligns their behavior with their principles and convictions. The author does concede, though, that the concept of ethical leadership is nebulous and has many moving parts. It could be challenging to assess ethical leadership abilities as a result.

Elementary school teachers in the Lugus District, and MBHTE-Division of Sulu, where they work and are presumably the recipients of skills exposed by Lugus District school administrators, present the researcher with the challenge of bringing attention to this issue and conducting research on it. Thus, this point of view influenced the design of the study, and the investigator collected primary data and information that helped the MBHTE - Sulu consider the real reasons behind certain educational problems as well as the duties and obligations of school administrators, especially their capacity for moral leadership.

In response to inquiries about leadership, Keinwood (2012) stated that a principal in the modern day needs to possess strong team-building abilities that enable teachers to collaborate with one another in any situation. Creating professional learning communities (PLCs) is even more significant in this environment; for instance, the principal is in charge of setting extremely specific expectations for PLC members' work.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators, as perceived by teachers of Lugus District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education in Sulu during the School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it seeks to find answers to the following queries upon its very completion:

1. What is the demographic profile of the elementary school teacher-respondents of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu in terms of;
 - 1.1 Gender;
 - 1.2 Educational Attainment;
 - 1.3 Civil Status; and

- 1.4 Length of Service?
2. What is the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators, as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu in the context of:
 - 2.1 Decisiveness;
 - 2.2 Integrity;
 - 2.3 Problem Solving; and
 - 2.4 Dependability?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu when data grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of:
 - 3.1 Gender;
 - 3.2 Educational Attainment;
 - 3.3 Civil Status; and
 - 3.4 Length of Service?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used survey descriptive research design. Survey research descriptive design is a research procedure which involves the survey research instrument to gathered information of elementary school administrator ethical leadership skills. Descriptive research was involved in the analysis of data based on the current existing situation that is the description of the elementary school administrator of ethical leadership skills in Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at 17 schools of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu Municipality of Lugus. It has eight (8) elementary schools level and nine (9) primary school level. Each school is managed by School Head (SH) or Teacher In-Charge (TIC) who are termed in this study as the school administrator. It is an island district accessible through the sea only.

Respondents of the Study

This study used all the school administrators and teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu. The study used purposive sampling design. The study was conducted in Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu, so the respondents were the teachers of Lugus District. The distribution of the respondents is shown in table A. The name of the schools is found on the left part below.

Table A

DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS

No.	Schools	Actual Teachers			Respondents		TOTAL
		Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	
1	Alu Duyong ES	4	9	13	3	11	14
2	Laud Alu PS	1	2	3	1	2	3
3	Lahud PS	1	3	4	1	3	4
4	Bas Nunuk ES	0	8	8	0	7	7
5	Bas Mangkallay ES	1	7	8	1	6	7
6	Lugus Central School	1	6	7	1	5	6
7	Bas Lugus CS-Annex	1	2	3	1	2	3
8	Parian Kayawan ES	1	8	9	1	7	8
9	Boli Pongpong PS	2	3	5	1	2	3
10	Rugasan ES	1	6	7	1	6	7
11	Gapas PS	1	2	3	1	2	3
12	Guimba Pait PS	1	5	6	1	4	5
13	Sibul PS	1	3	4	1	3	4
14	Tangkulan ES	5	10	15	4	10	14
15	Hadji Sali Tammang PS	0	4	4	0	3	3
16	Tubba Bas PS	0	3	3	0	2	2
17	Tingkangan ES	1	6	7	1	6	7
	TOTAL	22	87	109	19	81	100

Sampling Design

The purposive sampling design was used in the selection of respondents for the study. It is a design with a purpose and the purpose is to select 100 respondents of the study.

Research Instrument

The instrument of this study was adapted from the questionnaires of the Observer-Assessment for Breaking Ranks Leaders of the National Association of Elementary School Principals (NAESP, 2010) supported by the questionnaire of Precilla, et. al. (2016). The questionnaire was revised to suit the objectives of this study. This questionnaire is divided into two parts: Parts I inquires the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, educational attainment, civil status, and the length of service. Part II inquires the opinions on the leadership skills of elementary school administrators of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu in terms of decisiveness, integrity, problem solving, and dependability.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following sequence were followed by the researcher in data gathering:

1. Request approval from Sulu State College's Graduate Studies office.
2. Request approval from the MBHTE-Sulu office of the superintendent.
3. Present endorsement letter to the District Focal Person and School Principals.
4. The researcher personally gave the questionnaire to each teacher when the request for authorization was granted.
5. Upon completion of the questionnaire, the researcher will retrieve the questionnaire on the same or following day.
6. Upon completion of the questionnaires' retrieval, the researcher tallied the responses on the competition of raw data. The analysis and interpretation were done with the assistance of the thesis adviser.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The research questions served as a guide for this study. The statistical tools that were used are identified according to the nature of the problem. The problem, "What is the demographic profile of the elementary school teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu in terms of gender, educational attainment, civil status, and length of service?" frequently percentage distribution was used.

The problem, "What the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators is as viewed in the context of decisiveness, honesty, problem solving, and dependability by the instructors of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu? Standard deviation and mean were applied.

The problem, "Is there significant difference on the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed in the context of decisiveness, honesty, problem solving, and dependability by the instructors of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu?" Gender was assessed using the T-test, while duration of service, educational achievement, and civil status were assessed using a One-Way ANOVA.

The problem, "Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed in the context of decisiveness, honesty, problem solving, and dependability by the instructors of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu?" Pearson Product – Moment Correlation was used.

RESULTS

1. *What is the demographic profile of the elementary school teacher – respondents of Lugus District, MBHTE - Sulu in terms of 1.1 gender, 1.2 educational attainment, 1.3 civil status, and 1.4 length of service?*

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. Sixty - nine percent (69%) of the respondents are females and 31% are males.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	31	31%
Female	69	69%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment.

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment.

It shows that 66% of the respondents finished Baccalaureate Degree only while only 2% finished Doctorate Degree.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Baccalaureate Degree	66	66%
With M.A. Units	21	21%
Master's Degree	9	9%

With Doctorate units	2	2%
Doctorate Degree	2	2%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status.

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of civil status.

It showed that 65% of the respondents are married and only 6% are either widow or separated.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status.

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	29	29%
Married	65	65%
Widow/Separated	6	6%
TOTAL	100	100%

1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service.

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of length of service.

It showed that 35% of the teachers are 16 years and above already in service and only 14% are 5 years and below in service.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
5 years and below	14	14%
6 – 10 years	30	30%
11 – 15 years	21	21%
16 years and above	35	35%
TOTAL	100	100%

2. What is the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed in the context of decisiveness, honesty, problem solving, and dependability by the instructors of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu in the context of 2.1 decisiveness, 2.2 integrity, 2.3 problem solving, and 2.4 dependability?

Table 2.1 presents the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of decisiveness.

It showed that the respondents indicated from **often** to **sometimes** on the different statements in the context of decisiveness. Among those they indicated **often** are; my school head measures the possibility of success in its decision – making (mean = 3.850, SD = 1.048); and my school head is willing to consider other options when making decisions (mean = 3.790, SD = 1.320). For **sometimes**, some of the statements are; my school head imparts knowledge about the science of making decisions (mean = 3.450, SD = 1.486); and my school heads’ decision – making is influence by external stakeholders’ demands (mean = 3.350, SD = 1.336). The average mean of 3.622 means that ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators **often** influenced the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of decisiveness.

Table 2.1 Extent of the Ethical Leadership Skills of Elementary School Administrators as viewed by the Teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the Context of Decisiveness.

Decisiveness	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My school head evaluates the impact of the decision he/she makes.	3.720	1.349	Often
2. My school heads’ decision – making is transparent.	3.570	1.174	Often
3. My school heads’ decision – making is consistent.	3.650	1.234	Often
4. My school heads’ decision – making is influence by external stakeholders’ demands.	3.350	1.336	Sometimes
5. My school head quantifies the probability of success in its decision – making.	3.850	1.048	Often
6. My school head is open to using alternatives in its decision – making.	3.790	1.320	Often
7. My school head considers uncertainties in relation to its decision – making.	3.540	1.493	Often
8. My school head re – examines its decision – making as new information becomes available.	3.550	1.167	Often
9. My school head uses a structured approach in its decision – making.	3.570	.924	Often
10. My school head provides training in the science of decision – making.	3.450	1.486	Sometimes
AVERAGE	3.622		OFTEN

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never

Table 2.2 presents the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of integrity.

The respondents indicated *often* in almost all statements except in statement 4 where they indicated *sometimes* and that statement is; my school head update teachers on the school expenditures (mean = 3.440, SD = 1.493). For often, some of the statements are; my school head is trustworthy (mean = 4.480, SD = .759); my school head emphasize integrity in the performance of work (mean = 4.400, SD = 2.958); and my school head avoids spending the school MOOE on unnecessary things (mean = 4.360, SD = .732). The average mean of 4.065 means that ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators *often* influenced the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of integrity.

Table 2.2 Extent of the Ethical Leadership Skills of Elementary School Administrators as viewed by the Teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the Context of Integrity.

Integrity	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My school head is trustworthy.	4.480	.759	Often
2. My school head emphasize integrity in the performance of work.	4.400	2.958	Often
3. My school head provides a transparency board in school.	4.110	1.024	Often
4. My school head update teachers on the school expenditures.	3.440	1.493	Sometimes
5. My school head trust teachers to do their work even without his observation.	3.640	1.299	Often
6. My school head avoids spending the school MOOE on unnecessary things.	4.360	.732	Often
7. My school head has proven to us that he can be trusted.	4.040	1.363	Often
8. My school head demands integrity in dealing with the learners.	4.020	1.356	Often

9. My school head trusts the teacher's decision in dealing with the learners.	3.870	1.361	Often
10. My school head is trusted so much by the District Supervisor.	4.290	.729	Often
AVERAGE	4.065		OFTEN

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never

Table 2.3 presents the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of problem solving.

The respondents indicated *sometimes* in all statements in the context of problem solving. Some of those statements are; my school head understands everyone's interests (mean = 3.210, SD = 1.604); my school head reviews the results of his decisions (mean = 3.370, SD = 1.727); and my school head implement the best possible solution to the problem (mean = 3.460, SD = 1.778). The average mean of 3.301 means that ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators *sometimes* influenced the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of problem solving.

Table 2.3 Extent of the Ethical Leadership Skills of Elementary School Administrators as viewed by the Teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the Context of Problem Solving.

Problem Solving	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My school head identify the issues.	3.290	1.665	Sometimes
2. My school head understand everyone's interests.	3.210	1.604	Sometimes
3. My school head list the possible solutions.	3.330	1.710	Sometimes
4. My school head evaluate the options.	3.090	1.498	Sometimes
5. My school head select an option or options.	3.230	1.620	Sometimes
6. My school head document the agreement(s).	3.270	1.651	Sometimes
7. My school head agree on contingencies,			

monitoring, and evaluation.	3.470	1.784	Sometimes
8. My school head use trial and error in solving a problem.	3.290	1.671	Sometimes
9. My school head review the results of his decisions.	3.370	1.727	Sometimes
10. My school head implement the best possible solution to the problem.	3.460	1.778	Sometimes
AVERAGE	3.301		SOMETIMES

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never

Table 2.4 presents the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of dependability.

The respondents indicated from *often* to *sometimes* on the different statements in the context of decisiveness. For *often*, some of those statements are; my school head conducts a step – by – step procedure in problem solving (mean = 3.790, SD = 1.320); and my school heads' decision is stable (mean = 4.320, SD = 2.831). for *sometimes*, some of the statements are; my school head provides detached description of the problem (mean = 3.390, SD = 1.100); and my school head encourages teachers to participate in the analysis process of a problem (mean = 3.340, SD = 1.760). The average mean of 3.665 means that ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators *often* influenced the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of dependability.

Table 2.4 Extent of the Ethical Leadership Skills of Elementary School Administrators as viewed by the Teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu in the Context of Dependability.

Dependability	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My school head encourages teachers to participate in the analysis process of a problem.	3.340	1.760	Sometimes
2. My school head provides detached description	3.390	1.100	Sometimes

of the problem.			
3. My school head conducts a step – by – step procedure in problem solving.	3.790	1.320	Often
4. My school head is consistent with his/her decisions.	3.760	1.288	Often
5. My school head’s decision is reliable, steady, and trustworthy.	3.810	1.022	Often
6. My school heads’ decision is stable.	4.230	2.831	Often
7. My school head builds trust by holding himself/herself accountable.	3.490	1.210	Sometimes
8. My school head makes the teachers safe and secured with his decisions.	3.690	1.261	Often
9. My school head has the ability to provide services that can be trusted.	3.560	1.506	Often
10. My school heads’ credibility is tested.	3.590	1.190	Often
AVERAGE	3.665		OFTEN

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed in the context of decisiveness, honesty, problem solving, and dependability by the instructors of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu?

The t-test was used for gender since there are only two categories. The sig. value of 0.469 for decisiveness is greater than the p – value of .05, the sig. value of 0.790 for integrity is greater than the p – value of .05, the sig. value of 0.615 for problem solving is greater than the p – value of .05, and the sig. value of 0.660 for dependability is also greater than the p – value of .05. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as viewed by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE - Sulu when data are grouped according to their gender.

Table 3.1 t – test for Significant Difference in the Extent of Ethical Leadership Skills of Elementary School Administrators as viewed by the Teachers of Lugus District in terms of Gender.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	t	Sig.	Description
Decisiveness	Male	4.100	.630	0.63	28.490	.469	Not
	Female	4.730	.750				Significant
Integrity	Male	4.650	.550	0.27	29.150	.790	Not
	Female	4.380	.720				Significant
Problem Solving	Male	4.210	.810	0.44	28.650	.615	Not
	Female	4.650	.790				Significant
Dependability	Male	4.720	.580	0.50	27.590	.660	Not
	Female	4.220	.490				Significant

Significant at .05 level

In Table 3.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for educational attainment, civil status, and length of service.

The sig. value of 0.595 for educational attainment is greater than the p - value of .05, the sig. value of 0.341 for civil status is greater than the p-value at .05, and the sig. value of 0.414 for length of service is also greater than the sig. value of .05. It could only mean that the null hypothesis is accepted in terms of educational attainment, civil status, and length of service.

There is no significant difference in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE - Sulu when data are grouped according to their educational attainment, civil status, and length of service.

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of Ethical Leadership Skills of Elementary School Administrators as viewed in the context of decisiveness, honesty, problem solving, and dependability by the instructors of Lugus District, MBHTE-Sulu

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.	Interpretation
Educational Attainment	1.647	4	.412	.714	.595	Not Significant
Between Groups	54.812	95	.577			
Within Groups	54.459	99				
Total						
Civil Status						

Groups	Between	12.608	2	6.304	2.387	.341	Not Significant
		256.209	97	2.641			
	Within Groups	268.816	99				
Total							
Length of Service							
Groups	Between	12.253	3	4.084	1.371	.414	Not Significant
		285.951	96	2.979			
	Within Groups	298.204	99				
Total							

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu?

Pearson Product – Moment Correlation or Pearson r was used to determine if there is a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu.

The average value of $r = 0.852$ for decisiveness was interpreted as **very high correlation** while the average value of $r = 0.658$ for integrity was interpreted as **high correlation** at significant value of .05 two- tailed test, the average value of .820 for problem solving was interpreted as **very high correlation** and the average value of .830 for decisiveness was also interpreted as very high correlation.

Table 4. Significant Correlation in the Extent of Ethical Leadership Skills of Elementary School Administrators as Perceived by the Teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE - Sulu.

		Pearson r	Sig.	n	Description
Decisiveness	Integrity	.822	.000	100	Very High
	Problem Solving	.845	.000	100	Very High
	Dependability	.890	.000	100	Very High
	AVERAGE	.852			VERY HIGH
Integrity	Decisiveness	.666	.000	100	High
	Problem Solving	.533	.000	100	High
	Dependability	.775	.000	100	Very High
	AVERAGE	.658			HIGH
Problem Solving	Decisiveness	.835	.000	100	Very High
	Integrity	.809	.000	100	Very High
	Dependability	.817	.000	100	Very High
	AVERAGE	.820			VERY HIGH

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	Decisiveness	.789	.000	100	Very High
	Integrity	.880	.000	100	Very High
Dependability	Problem Solving	.821	.000	100	Very High
	AVERAGE	.830			VERY HIGH

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at $\alpha = .05$

Correlation Scales adapted from Hopkins (2002):

0.0 – 0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1 – 0.3 = Low; 0.3 – 0.5 = Moderate; 0.5 – 0.7 = High;
0.7 – 0.9 = Very High; 0.9 – 1.0 = Nearly Perfect

DISCUSSION

1. On the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender, educational attainment, civil status, and length of service.

The result showed that majority of the respondents are females, finished baccalaureate degree only, married, and 16 years and above in service.

It implies that the teachers of Lugus District are mostly females, most did not pursue graduate studies, with families of their own, and at one – third are at least 15 years and above in service.

2. On the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District MBHTE – Sulu in the context of decisiveness, integrity, problem solving, and dependability.

The teachers of Lugus District perceived the ethical leadership skills of their administrators District are **often** seen in terms of decisiveness, integrity, and dependability. However, it is **sometimes** seen in terms of problem solving.

The result implies that the teachers perceived their administrators to practiced ethical leadership most of the time in terms of decisiveness, integrity, and dependability, and practiced problem solving from time to time.

According to Plinio (2009), persuading others to act morally is not the challenging aspect of ethical leadership abilities. Instead, the ambiguities around accountability for issues that develop present the complexity of ethical leadership. An ethical leader must therefore accept accountability for the outcomes of his choices.

Frank (2002) asserts that a lack of trust is currently the largest issue facing both individuals and organizations. The "shadow side" of leadership has been blamed for this

lack of confidence. Therefore, it is critical that instructors feel comfortable entrusting school officials with their trust and that they can be relied upon.

3. On the Significant difference in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, educational attainment, civil status, and length of service.

There is no significant difference in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, educational attainment, civil status, and length of service.

The result implies that the different demographic profiles of the teachers of Lugus District cannot verify their perception on the extent of ethical leadership skills of their administrators.

4. On the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District, MBHTE – Sulu.

There is a **very high correlation** among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators of Lugus District in the context of decisiveness, integrity, and dependability. However, there is a **high correlation** in terms of problem solving.

The result simply implies that the ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators of Lugus District differ to some degree especially in the context of problem solving.

Conclusions

The following was concluded based on the findings of the study:

The majority of primary school teachers in the Lugus District are female; a small percentage are pursuing graduate degrees, a small percentage remain unmarried, and one-third have worked there for more than 15 years.

It only showed that elementary school administrators of Lugus District practiced ethical leadership skills in terms of decisiveness, integrity, and dependability most of the time. But, they also practiced problem solving from time to time.

The absence of difference in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District could only mean that regardless of profile, they all practiced ethical leadership skills.

The very high to high correlation in the extent of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators as perceived by the teachers of Lugus District could only mean that the different factors are interrelated to one another to some extent.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. A study on the effect of ethical leadership skills of elementary school administrators on the teachers' performance must be conducted.
2. Future researchers on the same topic should add variables like relevant trainings attended by administrators to see its effect on their leadership skills.
3. Teachers should constantly support their administrators for the good of the service.
4. Administrators should give their best in managing the school and serve as an inspiration and role model to the teachers.
5. Parents should try their best to support whatever endeavors the school will undertake for the good of their children.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, the ethical care of all participants—especially the teachers at MBHTE-Sulu—is of utmost importance. While researching significant topics, the researcher made a consistent effort to uphold the respondents' right to privacy.

First and foremost, a thorough informed consent form explaining the study's objectives, procedures, potential benefits and dangers, and confidentiality guidelines was given to each participant. Furthermore, in situations where the respondents' individual information was unrelated to the trial data, every trial data point was meticulously anonymized. In order to protect participant privacy, data collection was done in a private setting, and the gathered information was stored in a safe archive that the researchers alone could access. In a same vein, respect was shown to every member notwithstanding differences in opinions and views. Furthermore, the researchers endeavored to furnish the participants with a safe and hospitable atmosphere, enabling them to freely discuss their experiences.

REFERENCES

- Angeles, Eduardo P. (2010). Leadership - Key Element in Organizational Management: The Modern Teacher Vol. 59.
- Frank, D. G. (2002). Meeting the ethical challenges of leadership. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 28(1/2), 81.

- Plinio, A. J., Young, Judith, M., & Lavery, L. M. (2010). The state of ethics in our society: A clear call for action. *International Journal of Disclosure & Governance*, 7(3), 172- 197.
- Yukl, G. A. (2006). *Leadership in Organizations* (6th Ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson/Prentice Hall.